

Terpenoids and Related Compounds-XVI¹. Terpenoids of the Bark of *Rhododendron falconeri* Sm.

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Betulinic acid, taraxeryl acetate, taraxerol, β -sitosterol and a new triterpenoid, C₃₂H₅₂O₃, have been isolated from the bark of *Rhododendron falconeri* Sm. The new triterpenoid has been shown from chemical transformations and Mass Spectrometric data to be uvaol 3-acetate.

Rhododendron falconeri Sm. is a tree abundantly distributed over East Nepal to Bhutan³. Recently Rangaswami *et al*⁴ have reported the isolation of ursolic acid, dendropanoxide, taraxerene and taraxerol from the leaves of *R. falconeri*. The present communication deals with the chemical investigation of the bark of the aforesaid plant.

The benzene extract of the bark was digested with ether and filtered. The ether-soluble portion was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The acidic portion has been shown to be betulinic acid by its conversion to methyl betulinate.

The neutral fraction on chromatography over activated alumina furnished first a solid m.p. 295-297°, (α)_D+8.9° (CHCl₃) which was identified as taraxeryl acetate. It was followed by a new compound, C₃₂H₅₂O₃, m.p. 258-261°, (α)_D+79.6°(CHCl₃), designated as solid A. The third crystalline compound that came out of the column was identified as taraxerol via its acetate. Further elution of the column furnished β -sitosterol, which was also converted into its acetate and identified by comparison with an authentic specimen.

- (I) R = R' = H
 (II) R = R' = Ac
 (III) R = H, R' = Ac

Figure - 1.

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4. S. Rangaswami and K. Sambomurthy, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1957, **46A**, 245.

The I.R. spectrum of solid A, $C_{32}H_{52}O_3$ (M^+484), showed bands at 3550 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl), 1720 and 1250 cm^{-1} (acetate) and 810 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond). On alkaline hydrolysis it afforded a diol, $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$, m.p. $226\text{--}228^\circ$, $(\alpha)_D + 71.4^\circ$ (CHCl_3), which showed I.R. band at 3380 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl) but no band in the carbonyl region. Acetylation of solid A yielded a diacetate, $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$, m.p. $148\text{--}152^\circ$. The above diol and the diacetate were found to be identical (mixed m.p. and I.R.) with the respective authentic specimens of uvaol (I) and uvaol diacetate (II). These information led us to characterise solid A as uvaol monoacetate. That the acetoxy group was actually present at C_3 in solid A was shown from the mass spectrometric fragmentation pattern of solid A. Hence solid A was uvaol 3-acetate (III).

The mass spectrum (Chart I) of solid A(III) showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 484, together with the ions at m/e 424 (M-60) and 453 (M-31) corresponding to the loss of CH_3COOH (60) and CH_2OH (31) respectively. Retro-Diels Alder fragmentation⁵ of the molecule gave the ions at m/e 249 (rings A and B) and m/e 234 (rings D and E).

Elimination of 60 mass units (AcOH) from the former resulted in the formation of the ion at m/e 189 and unequivocally located the presence of the acetoxy group at C_3 . On the other hand loss of 18 (H_2O) and 31 (CH_2OH) mass units from the ion at m/e 234 gave rise to peaks at m/e 216 and 203 respectively. The latter two peaks fixed the attachment of the CH_2OH group at C_{17} .

CHART - I.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s are uncorrected. The petroleum ether used had b.p. 60-80°.

Benzene Extraction of the bark of R. falconeri : Dried and finely powdered bark (2.5 Kg) was extracted with benzene in a soxhlet apparatus for 10 hr. The partially crystalline mass obtained after evaporation of benzene was taken up in ether and filtered from some slimy material. The ether solution was extracted with cold 6% KOH solution, when a flocculent precipitate appeared in the aqueous phase. The ether solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to yield a partially crystalline neutral material (20 g).

Acidic fraction : The above aqueous alkaline phase containing the insoluble potassium salt of acidic constituents was acidified with 6(N)HCl and the resulting solution was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to yield a crystalline acidic material (22 g.).

Methyl betulinate : The aforementioned crystalline acidic material (3 g.) was esterified with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (prepared from 3 g. of nitrosomethylurea). Usual working up furnished a crude methyl ester (3 g.), m.p. 190-210°, which was chromatographed over alumina (50 g, deactivated with 1.5 ml of 10% aqueous acetic acid). Elution of the column with a mixture of pet. ether and benzene (3:2) gave a solid (1.62 g.), m.p. 208-218°. On several crystallisations from methanol the above compound yielded pure methyl ester, m.p. 220-222°, $(\alpha)_D + 4.3^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of methyl betulinate. (Found : C, 78.66; H, 10.86. Calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$: C, 79.10; H, 10.71%).

Examination of the neutral fraction : The partially crystalline neutral residue (20 g.) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (320 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (2:3) furnished a crystalline solid (2.20 g.), m.p. 290-295°.

Taraxeryl acetate : The above crystalline compound on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave a solid, m.p. 295-297°, $(\alpha)_D + 8.9^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of taraxeryl acetate. (Found : C, 82.24; H, 11.09. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Uvaol-3-acetate (III) : Elution of the above column with a mixture of benzene and ether (4:1) furnished a crystalline compound which on several crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and methanol and finally from acetone afforded a solid, m.p. 258-261°, $(\alpha)_D + 79.6^\circ$ (CHCl_3). (Found : C, 79.21, 79.67; H, 10.59, 10.87. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 79.28; H, 10.81%). *I.R* : Peaks at 3550 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl), 1720, 1250 cm^{-1} (acetate) and 810 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond).

Mass Spec : Molecular ion peak at m/e 484. Other important peaks at m/e 424, 453, 249, 234, 216, 189 and 203.

Uvaol (I) : A mixture of the above uvaol 3-acetate (III, 0.1 g.), benzene (3 ml.) and 10% methanolic KOH (3.6 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr. The mixture was then cooled diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a compound (0.1 g.), m.p. 224-228°, which on crystallisation from acetone yielded a solid m.p. 226-228°, $(\alpha)_D + 71.4^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical

(mixed m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic specimen of uvaol (I). (Found : C, 81.48; H, 11.12. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.39; H, 11.38%). I.R. Peak at 3380 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl), but no peak in the carbonyl region.

Uvaol diacetate (II) : A mixture of uvaol 3-acetate (III, 0.1 g.), acetic anhydride (1 ml.) and pyridine (1 ml) was heated on the water bath for 1 hr. and allowed to stand overnight. The crude acetate that crystallised out of the reaction mixture was filtered and crystallised from methanol to give a solid, m.p. $148\text{-}152^\circ$, identical (mixed m.p. and I.R.) with an authentic sample of uvaol diacetate (II).

Taraxerol : Elution of the above column with a mixture of benzene and ether (2:3) furnished a crystalline solid (0.4 g.), m.p. $272\text{-}276^\circ$ which was directly acetylated with acetic anhydride (4 ml.) and pyridine (4 ml.) as above. The crude acetate that crystallised out of the reaction mixture was filtered and recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and methanol to yield a solid, m.p. $297\text{-}299^\circ$, identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen of taraxeryl acetate.

β -Sitosterol : Further elution of the column with ether yielded a greenish gummy solid (0.60 g.), m.p. $120\text{-}122^\circ$ which was directly acetylated with acetic anhydride (6 ml.) and pyridine (6 ml.). Usual working up gave the crude acetate (0.55 g.) m.p. $110\text{-}112^\circ$, which on crystallisation from acetone afforded a solid, m.p. $120\text{-}122^\circ$, $(\alpha)_D - 28^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found : C, 81.48; H, 11.36. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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